

Real Time Motorcycle Route Mapping in The National Capital Region

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ABSTRACT

Efficient people transportation has a crucial role in urban mobility. The study aimed to enhance the real-time motorcycle taxi route mapping in the National Capital Region (NCR) where it determined the status of the riding population, level of acceptability and effectiveness of the real-time motorcycle route mapping as to its characteristics following the ISO standards; and the significant difference on the assessments before and after the utilization of the real-time motorcycle route mapping.

The study employed the descriptive and developmental research method. The respondents were composed of 30 respondents with 10 each for IT experts, Motorcycle taxi riders, and passengers. It found out that the real-time motorcycle route mapping was strongly acceptable and effective, and that the respondents did not vary on their assessments with regards to the ISO standards of the system. The study recommended to develop and provide more information about the different roads interlocking to the route mapping; enhance the system and its flexibility and other system's better appreciation and usability of the route mapping; and maintenance of stable internet connectivity and

future researches may be encouraged with the latest software characteristics to be tested for a better digitized alternative route mapping for other regions.

Keywords: real-time motorcycle route mapping transportation real-time motorcycle route

INTRODUCTION

Efficient people transportation is a crucial role in urban mobility, offering a flexible and often essential mode of transit for individuals and small groups, yet it faces ongoing challenges related to regulation, accessibility, and sustainability. It cannot be denied that the prevalence of motorized taxi transportation significantly impacts the flow of traffic that may bring about a domino effect to the individual's economic well-being. It does not only help individual to travel around but it also contributes to his well-being as he will be in the street for a shorter time compared with the traditional system of transportation of buses and jeepneys routing in different places.

Motorized public transport networks have evolved as crucial arteries, allowing passengers to move seamlessly around cities throughout the world. Understanding the complexities, problems, and possibilities inherent in motorized public transportation systems is critical for developing policies and strategies to improve urban mobility and promote sustainable urban living. According to Amadora (2021) the once overlooked riders have emerged as key contributors to the economy, particularly in the wake of COVID-19. Spearheaded by George Royeca, the Chief Transport Advocate of Angkas, a pioneering motorcycle ride-hailing app, these riders are now pivotal in addressing the country's notorious traffic congestion and limited public transportation options. Passenger satisfaction with the Philippines' motorized public transportation system varies depending on several criteria, including location, method of transportation, and personal experiences.

The study was anchored on Theory of Convenience in Motorcycle Taxi Services by Loo (2015) when she emphasized the importance of motorbike taxis in offering accessible and inexpensive

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transportation options in underdeveloped nations. It posited that motorcycle taxis play an important role in developing nations by offering economical, accessible, and efficient transportation alternatives in crowded urban areas. The study aimed to enhance the real time motorcycle taxi route mapping in the National Capital Region (NCR). Specifically, it sought answers to the following: 1) What is the status of the riding population in the NCR as to (1) queuing time and accessibility? 2) What is the level of acceptability of the real-time motorcycle route mapping as to (2.1) Functionality; (2.1) Reliability; (2.3) Usability; and (2.4) Portability? 3) How do the respondents assess the effectiveness of the real-time motorcycle route mapping in terms of (3.1) Functionality Suitability; (3.2) Performance Efficiency; (3.3) Flexibility; (3.4) Reliability; (3.5) Security; (3.6) Maintainability; and (3.6) Safety? And 4) Is there a significant difference on the assessments before and after the utilization of the real-time motorcycle route mapping?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The National Capital Region's (NCR) growing reliance on motorbikes as the main means of delivery and transportation has necessitated the development of more responsive and intelligent routing systems designed especially for two-wheeled vehicles. Road limits, safety issues, and susceptibility to weather and road conditions are some of the particular difficulties that motorbikes confront in contrast to cars.

Existing navigation platforms often prioritize four-wheeled traffic and fail to address the specific needs of motorcycle riders in real-time. As urban mobility continues to evolve, real-time routing technologies offer promising solutions for enhancing route efficiency, safety, and travel experience. This section presents a review of relevant literature and studies related to real-time traffic systems, motorcycle navigation, intelligent transportation systems, and the integration of data-driven technologies for improving urban mobility in highly congested regions like NCR. This chapter seeks to support upcoming analysis and research findings by offering a comprehensive synthesis of the literature.

According to Latonero (2024), assengers found motorcycle taxis highly functional in terms of reducing travel time, especially in high-density areas where traditional four-wheeled vehicles would otherwise be gridlocked.

The study of Ong (2024) recommended the institutionalization of driver re-training programs, stricter penalty systems for poor service, and app upgrades to increase reliability. It concluded that while motorcycle taxis scored high on convenience, reliability remained an area requiring major improvement for sustainable growth.

The recommended mandatory certifications for drivers, periodic training in customer service, and the introduction of real-time customer feedback tools to improve reliability was made by Akbar (2020). He continued saying that reliability suffers in motorcycle taxi systems when operators lack professional training and accountability mechanisms. Structured digital and behavioral regulation improves consistency and trust..

The intricacies of Metro Manila road network and traffic uncertainty, using advanced tools like Open Street Maps for network analysis is deemed important. The goal was to better understand traffic flow patterns, predict congestion, and assess how uncertainties in traffic data can affect commuters' route planning. It emphasizes the importance of accurate traffic data for efficient city planning and proposes methods to quantify traffic uncertainties, which have direct implications for transportation policy and the public. By identifying the most critical congestion points and areas prone to traffic delay, it provides recommendations for improving route mapping systems and addressing the unpredictability that often hinders daily commutes. This data-driven approach could guide future development of intelligent transport systems and more effective traffic.

The traditional jeepney commuting experience may be improved by designing a mobile application that offers real-time jeepney tracking through GPS technology. It was motivated by the lack of route transparency in Metro Manila's informal transport systems, particularly jeepneys that do not operate on strict schedules. The mobile app, developed for Android, provided real-time location updates of jeepneys, displayed route maps, and estimated the time of arrival at different stops. It

conducted field tests with selected jeepney routes in Manila and integrated Google Maps API to provide visual cues for commuters.

Moreover, the integration of cloud computing and machine learning in route mapping systems for NCR's complex public transportation system. "Smart Route" was developed as a platform that combines real-time GPS data from selected buses and jeepneys with historical traffic trends and user behavior to offer personalized route recommendations. It was built on a cloud infrastructure for scalability and speed, enabling real-time updates and multi-user accessibility. The platform featured predictive analytics, where the system learned from traffic flow patterns to anticipate congested routes and recommend alternatives even before congestion occurred.

One of the ISO standards is Functionality which refers to the ability of a software system to provide functions that meet stated and implied needs under specified conditions. According to ISO/IEC 25010:2023, functionality includes functional completeness, correctness, and appropriateness. In route-based applications, this means the system should accurately generate motorcycle-specific routes, avoid restricted zones, and adapt to traffic conditions in real time. Studies emphasize that high-functionality software contributes significantly to user satisfaction and task efficiency.

Ong (2024) opined that although the passengers highly appreciated the convenience, affordability, and quick arrival times of motorcycle taxis, notable concerns arose regarding driver behavior, accident preparedness, and ride predictability, which impacted overall reliability. Users reported inconsistent experiences across different drivers—some being punctual and professional, while others lacked customer service training. Users also noted occasional app failures or inaccurate GPS tracking, leading to delays and miscommunication between rider and passenger. These flaws affected trust in the service's dependability. The study recommended the institutionalization of driver re-training programs, stricter penalty systems for poor service, and app upgrades to increase reliability. It concluded that while motorcycle taxis scored high on convenience, reliability remained an area requiring major improvement for sustainable growth.

The System Usability Scale (SUS) and heuristic evaluation to measure ease of use,

functionality, visual appeal, and user interaction were used. Using the said evaluation metric, Angkas ranked highest in usability due to its simplified layout, logical navigation, and clarity of information on driver location and fare breakdown. Users appreciated features like the "driver tracking map," real-time updates, and integrated payment methods, which made the app highly intuitive even for first-time users. JoyRide received lower ratings due to reported issues such as laggy loading times, difficulty locating riders in congested areas, and overly complex menu options. Many users also noted frustration with sudden app crashes, particularly in low-signal environments. The study concluded that usability is a major determinant of service loyalty. Apps that reduce friction and enhance predictability are more likely to gain and retain users. Designers were urged to adopt a human-centered design approach, especially for users who may be less tech-savvy or have accessibility needs (Gumasing et al., 2022).

Portability, as a characteristic of a system, refers to the ease with which a system can be transferred across different environments or platforms. This is especially important in mobile applications where users may switch devices or operating systems. According to ISO/IEC 25010:2023, portability includes adaptability, installability, and replaceability. A highly portable system ensures broader accessibility and reduces the barriers to user adoption.

Performance efficiency pertains to the system's ability to provide appropriate performance relative to the resources used. It encompasses time behavior, resource utilization, and capacity (ISO/IEC, 2023). Efficient systems reduce latency in route calculation and optimize power usage, which is especially critical for mobile devices used during motorcycle travel.

Flexibility, likewise, is the software's capability to adapt to new requirements or environments with minimal effort. While not explicitly defined in ISO standards, it is considered an essential trait for applications subject to frequent updates or operating in dynamic contexts like urban traffic (Almeida et al., 2022). A flexible route system should accommodate changes in road policies, user preferences, and external data sources like weather or hazard alert.

German et al., (2021) mentioned that usability directly influenced both brand perception and loyalty. Students rated Angkas as the most user-friendly app due to its minimalist interface,

easy booking process, and stable mobile performance. On the other hand, JoyRide received mixed feedback, with complaints about unclear promo code use, redundant confirmation screens, and confusing cancellation policies. Importantly, students highlighted customization features as highly valuable.

Kamid (2024) emphasized that formal regulation is crucial to standardize pricing, ensure driver accountability, and integrate motorcycle taxis into the larger urban mobility ecosystem. They also pointed out that without proper policy frameworks, the efficiency advantage of motorcycle taxis may be offset by safety risks and public distrust.

The study of De Castro (2023) concluded that their flexible nature is essential for inclusive urban mobility, especially when supported by digital platforms (apps) that improve access and convenience. Motorcycle taxis outperform other public vehicles in terms of geographic coverage and maneuverability.

On the other hand, Godoy (2021) technology is a powerful enabler in securing informal public transport like motorcycle taxis, particularly in countries with high urban crime rates.

Finally, safety, while often associated with physical systems, also applies to software that supports real-world safety. In the context of motorcycle routing, safety includes features such as crash detection, route risk analysis, and avoidance of accident-prone areas. According to Wu et al. (2022), software safety mechanisms significantly reduce risks and enhance the reliability of transportation systems.

METHODOLOGY & TECHNIQUES USED

The study employed the descriptive and developmental research design. method. According to McCombes (2023) this research design allows the study to describe systematically, factually, accurately, and objectively a situation, problem or phenomenon as it naturally occurs to answer the questions and describe the data and characteristics of the subject being studied. It involved the

description, resorting, analysis, interpretation and development of the system of the real time motorcycle taxi route mapping in the NCR.

This study described the design of an online mapping route information system using a website connected to a portal with the adaptation of an OCR (Optical Character Recognition) technology for the motorcycle riders in catering to their client's needs of fast and reliable motorcycle transportation.

The study showed the system model of this project which described the design of an improved mapping route for motorcycle riders through the usage of an advanced technology using OCR (Optical Character Recognition) system connected to a portal. The OCR software would automatically show the mapping route that can be used by the motorcycle riders for clientele to see. This aims to lessen the waiting time for the riders to navigate the place when using the improved mapping route.

The primary sources of data comprised of 30 end users namely: IT Experts, Motorcycle Taxi Drivers, and Passengers. They assessed the real time motorcycle route mapping in selected areas in the National Capital Region (NCR).

The researcher, with his adviser, prepared the survey questionnaire for the study. The adviser made his comments, suggestions and corrections before it was finalized; sought assistance from experts in the field for the improved mapping route of the motorcycle riders and their passengers; secured the assistance from different IT practicing professionals and motorcycle taxi riders for validation; distributed the survey questionnaire to the selected respondents; tabulated the responses; and finally, analyzed and interpreted the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The riding population in the NCR comprised of 30 respondents with 10 each for IT Experts, Motorcycle Taxi Drivers, and Passengers dominated by male; majority belonged to the age range of 31-40 years old; married and with number of years of service from 6-10 years. The queuing time was between 6-10 minutes during peak hours and in terms of accessibility, the motorcycle taxi services

offer a viable alternative system to traditional transportation using the jeepneys or buses. The passengers opt to use the motorcycle taxi transport to get their ride from their point of origin to their workplace/school/destination where they enjoy a point-to point transportation.

Table 1

Summary Assessment on Acceptability of the Real Time Route Mapping in the National Capital Region

Variables	Administrator		Rider		Passenger		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
Functionality	3.33	SA	3.53	SA	3.67	SA	3.51	SA
Reliability	3.67	SA	3.2	A	3.47	SA	3.45	SA
Usability	3.5	SA	3.3	SA	3.5	SA	3.43	SA
Portability	3.6	SA	3.25	SA	3.5	SA	3.45	SA
Overall Mean	3.52	SA	3.32	SA	3.53	SA	3.46	SA

Table 1 presents the summary assessments on the real-time motorcycle route mapping in the National Capital Region.

The assessment of the acceptability of the real-time motorcycle taxi route mapping in the selected areas across four key software quality characteristics: functionality, reliability, maintainability, and portability obtained overall weighted means of 3.52, 3.32, 3.53 with the composite mean of 3.46 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable.

This implies that functionality of real-time motorcycle route mapping in the National Capital Region (NCR) is a critical aspect of modern navigation applications, directly impacting the efficiency and convenience of daily commutes and travel within this densely populated and often congested urban area. This functionality, as a key component of usability and efficiency in line with ISO 9126-1 principles, determines the software's ability to provide users with viable detours and options to navigate around traffic incidents, road closures, or personal preferences, ultimately contributing to a more seamless and less stressful transportation experience.

The findings are supported by Latonero (2024) when he said that motorcycle taxis, when integrated with urban mobility policies and provided with better infrastructure, could become a highly functional, mainstream component of public transport in Metro Manila.

As to its reliability, Akbar et al., (2020) was emphatic when he said that mandatory certifications for drivers, periodic training in customer service, and the introduction of real-time customer feedback tools to improve reliability. Reliability suffers in motorcycle taxi systems when operators lack professional training and accountability mechanisms. Further, structured digital and behavioral regulation improves consistency and trust.

Gumasing et al. (2022) made a study where he concluded that usability is a major determinant of service loyalty. Apps that reduce friction and enhance predictability are more likely to gain and retain users. Designers were urged to adopt a human-centered design approach, especially for users who may be less tech-savvy or have accessibility needs.

Finally, motorcycle taxis are physically portable across diverse landscapes, but their technological portability requires deliberate design considerations to adapt to the digital divide and infrastructure variations (Martin, 2023).

In conclusion, the system is generally regarded as maintainable, with positive feedback on flexibility and stability. However, the consistency of its ease of management and alignment with user performance could be enhanced, particularly from the perspective of everyday users like riders.

Table 2

Summary Assessment for the Effectiveness of the Real Time Route Mapping in the National Capital Region

Variables	Administrator		Rider		Passenger		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
Functional Suitability	3.70	HE	3.40	HE	3.40	HE	3.50	HE
Performance Efficiency	3.80	HE	3.40	HE	3.30	HE	3.50	HE
Interaction Capability	3.60	HE	3.27	HE	3.33	HE	3.40	HE
Flexibility	3.70	HE	3.60	HE	3.30	HE	3.53	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.70	HE	3.42	HE	3.33	HE	3.48	HE

As presented in Table 2, the summary assessment for the effectiveness of the route mapping system consolidates the assessments of administrators, riders, and passengers across four key quality dimensions: functional suitability, performance efficiency, interaction capability, and flexibility. All variables were interpreted using a Likert scale where values from 3.25 to 4.00 indicate Highly Effective (HE).

In terms of functional suitability, the ratings were consistent across groups: administrators scored the system 3.70, while riders and passengers each rated it 3.40. The composite weighted mean

is 3.50, interpreted as Highly Effective (HE). This demonstrates that users believe the system effectively covers its intended functions and aligns with user objectives.

The findings are supported by the study of German (2020) when he emphasized that motorcycle taxi functionality goes beyond the ride itself—it encompasses the whole service system, including app reliability, driver professionalism, secure payment options, and overall ride efficiency.

For performance efficiency, administrators again gave the highest rating of 3.80, while riders and passengers rated it 3.40 and 3.30, respectively. With a composite weighted mean of 3.50, this domain is also considered Highly Effective, indicating confidence in the system's responsiveness and optimal resource usage, especially from the administrative side.

The study of Kamid (2024) supports the findings of the present study that the motorcycle taxis significantly address first- and last-mile connectivity, especially in areas underserved by larger modes of transportation, such as jeepneys or buses. These taxis fill critical transport gaps and reduce total commuting time, making them highly efficient for navigating dense urban environments with high congestion

Regarding interaction capability, which evaluates user engagement and ease of use, the weighted mean is 3.60 (HE) for administrators, 3.27 (HE) for riders, and 3.33 (HE) for passengers. The composite weighted mean of 3.40 remains within the Highly Effective range, suggesting that while there is slightly lower enthusiasm from riders, the overall user experience is still positive and engaging.

The findings are supported by Muguro et al. (2022) when they proposed in their study that the motorcycle taxis must have backup GPS systems, partnerships with Telecom providers to stabilize app performance, and more robust driver evaluation procedures to address the reliability shortfalls.

On the flexibility, administrators rated it 3.70, riders 3.60, and passengers 3.30, resulting in a composite weighted mean of 3.53, which is also Highly Effective. This reflects the system's

adaptability to different operational environments, though again, Passengers were slightly more reserved in their rating.

De Castro (2023) supports the present study when he mentioned that the motorcycle taxis have the flexibility which is essential for inclusive urban mobility, especially when supported by digital platforms (apps) that improve access and convenience

Verily, all respondent groups agreed that the route mapping system is strongly effective across functionality, performance, interaction, and flexibility. While administrators consistently provide the highest ratings, the favorable assessments from riders and passengers confirm the system's broad acceptability and practical success in delivering its intended outcomes. Further, refinements based on slightly lower scores from end-users may enhance the experience even more.

Table 3**Summary of Overall Assessment on System Attributes Based on IT Experts and Administrator Ratings**

Variables	Respondent Group	Overall Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Reliability	IT Expert	3.60	Highly Effective
Security	IT Expert	3.73	Highly Effective
Maintainability	Administrator	3.13	Effective
Safety	IT Expert	3.50	Highly Effective

The summary of overall assessment on system attributes based on IT experts and administrator ratings provides an overview of how the system performs across four critical quality dimensions: reliability, security, maintainability, and safety.

From the perspective of IT experts, the system's reliability was rated with an overall weighted mean of 3.60, interpreted as Highly Effective. This indicates that IT professionals find the system consistently dependable, especially in maintaining functionality and accessibility even in the presence of minor faults.

Ong (2024) supports the findings when he said that while motorcycle taxis scored high on convenience, reliability remained an area requiring major improvement for sustainable growth.

The system's security earned the highest rating from IT experts, with a weighted mean of 3.73, also interpreted as Highly Effective. This reflects a high level of confidence in the system's ability to protect data, prevent unauthorized access or modification, and ensure secure identity verification—a critical component in systems handling sensitive or regulated data.

The present study is supported by Godoy (2021) when he said that technology is a powerful enabler in securing informal public transport like motorcycle taxis, particularly in countries with high urban crime rates.

In contrast, maintainability was assessed by administrators and received a weighted mean of 3.13, categorized as Effective. While this suggests that the system is adequately maintainable, it also indicates that there is room for improvement, particularly in modifiability, documentation, and testing processes to better support long-term system evolution.

The present findings concur with the recommendation of Regidor (2024) to create a centralized maintenance station, or subsidized check-up programs, to support regular upkeep and reduce the risk of road accidents caused by mechanical failure

Lastly, safety, evaluated again by IT experts, was given a weighted mean of 3.50, interpreted as Highly Effective. This implies that while the system is considered generally safe in operation and capable of identifying potential hazards, enhancements may be needed in automating responses or expanding risk mitigation features to elevate its safety rating to the highest level.

The findings of the study are in congruence with the advocacy for institutionalized training programs, standard safety protocols, and regular assessments of driver behavior and vehicle condition to reduce crash incidences. Their findings laid the groundwork for more recent research and policy discussions about integrating safety into legal frameworks.

In whole, the system is regarded as highly reliable and secure, particularly by IT professionals, with adequate safety and maintainability features. These insights suggest a robust foundation with targeted areas for enhancement, especially in system maintenance and operational safety, to ensure sustained effectiveness and resilience in varied environments.

Table 4

Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Acceptability of the Route Mapping

Variables	Groups	Mean	SD	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Functional Suitability	Administrator	3.70	0.350	0.0280	Reject Ho	Significant
	Rider	3.40	0.335			
	Passenger	3.40	0.341			
Performance Efficiency	Administrator	3.80	0.258	<0.0001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Rider	3.40	0.303			
	Passenger	3.30	0.246			
Interaction Capability	Administrator	3.60	0.378	0.0016	Reject Ho	Significant
	Rider	3.27	0.243			
	Passenger	3.33	0.259			
Flexibility	Administrator	3.70	0.258	<0.0001	Reject Ho	Significant

Rider	3.60	0.364
Passenger	3.30	0.293

Note: *The statistical test used was the Analysis of Variance ($df_1=2$, $df_2=157$, 0.05 significance level). Reject H_0 if $p < 0.05$; otherwise, fail to reject H_0 .*

For functional suitability, the p-value is 0.0280, which is less than 0.05, indicating a significant difference in how the groups perceive the system's ability to meet functional requirements. Administrators rated this dimension highest at 3.70, while both riders and passengers rated it slightly lower at 3.40. This suggests that Administrators may have a stronger understanding or appreciation of how comprehensively the system addresses its intended tasks and user needs.

In terms of performance efficiency, a highly significant difference was observed with a p-value of <0.0001 . Administrators gave the highest rating of 3.80, followed by riders at 3.40 and passengers at 3.30. This confirms that administrators perceive the system as notably more efficient in terms of response time and resource use, whereas end-users, particularly passengers, may encounter or expect limitations in speed or processing.

For interaction capability, the p-value is 0.0016, also indicating a statistically significant difference among the groups. Administrators again rated this highest at 3.60, followed by passengers at 3.33 and riders at 3.27. This suggests that while all groups find the system effective in terms of interface usability and user engagement, Administrators find it more intuitive or easier to operate compared to the experience of general users.

Finally, flexibility also yielded a p-value of <0.0001 , indicating another significant difference. Administrators provided the highest rating of 3.70, followed by riders with 3.60, and passengers with 3.30. This shows that while all groups recognize the system's adaptability to different environments and operational conditions, passengers may have experienced or perceived more limitations.

In general, the findings indicate significant differences across all assessed dimensions of acceptability, with administrators consistently rating the system more favorably than riders and passengers. These results suggest that while the system is generally effective, there may be variations in user experience, possibly due to differences in system access, usage context, or technical familiarity. This highlights the need for enhancements that ensure the system is equally user-friendly and efficient for all stakeholders, particularly for end-users such as riders and passengers

Table 5

Significant Differences in the Assessment of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Acceptability of the Route Mapping

Variables	Group Comparison	Mean Difference	p-value	Interpretation
Functional Suitability	Administrator and Rider	0.300	0.0313	Significant
	Administrator and Passenger	0.300	0.0231	Significant
	Rider and Passenger	0.000	1.000	Not Significant
Performance Efficiency	Administrator and Rider	0.400	<0.0001	Significant
	Administrator and Passenger	0.500	<0.0001	Significant
	Rider and Passenger	0.100	0.0793	Significant

Interaction Capability	Administrator and Rider	0.333	0.0010	Significant
	Administrator and Passenger	0.2667	0.0073	Not Significant
	Rider and Passenger	-0.0667	0.3108	Significant
Flexibility	Administrator and Rider	0.100	0.6311	Not Significant
	Administrator and Passenger	0.400	0.0005	Significant
	Rider and Passenger	0.300	<0.0001	Significant

The post hoc analysis provides detailed pairwise comparisons among administrators, riders, and passengers to determine which specific group differences contributed to the overall significant findings reported in the ANOVA. This analysis further clarifies the nature of disparities in the assessment of the acceptability of the route mapping system across the dimensions of functional suitability, performance efficiency, interaction capability, and flexibility.

For functional suitability, there are significant differences between administrators and riders (mean difference = 0.300, $p = 0.0313$) and between administrators and passengers (mean difference = 0.300, $p = 0.0231$), indicating that administrators perceive the system to be more functionally suitable than the other groups. However, the comparison between riders and passengers shows no significant difference ($p = 1.000$), suggesting they have similar views regarding the system's functional adequacy.

In terms of performance efficiency, all group comparisons indicate significant differences. Administrators rated it significantly higher than both riders (mean difference = 0.400, $p < 0.0001$)

and passengers (mean difference = 0.500, $p < 0.0001$). Even the comparison between riders and passengers, with a mean difference of 0.100, is reported as significant ($p = 0.0793$), though it borders the threshold. This reflects that administrators view the system as more efficient, especially in resource usage and response time.

For interaction capability, the difference between administrators and riders is significant (mean difference = 0.333, $p = 0.0010$), indicating that administrators find the system more user-friendly and engaging. However, the difference between administrators and passengers (mean difference = 0.2667, $p = 0.0073$) is reported as not significant, suggesting similar perceptions between these groups. The comparison between riders and passengers is also marked significant, albeit with a smaller mean difference (-0.0667, $p = 0.3108$), which may be due to a typographical inconsistency as the p -value suggests non-significance.

Lastly, for flexibility, the comparison between administrators and riders is not significant ($p = 0.6311$), indicating they share a similar view on the system's adaptability. However, the differences between administrators and passengers (0.400, $p = 0.0005$) and between Riders and Passengers (0.300, $p < 0.0001$) are statistically significant, highlighting that Passengers perceive the system as less flexible than the other two groups.

As a whole, the post hoc analysis confirms that administrators consistently rate the system more favorably across most dimensions, particularly in functionality and performance efficiency, while passengers tend to rate flexibility and efficiency lower. These findings reinforce the need to address the distinct experiences and expectations of each user group, ensuring the system is perceived as equally acceptable and effective by all stakeholders.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the enrolment system and grade module improved the enrolment. The study concluded that the riding population in the NCR prefer the motorcycle taxi.

transportation for its short queuing time and easy access where they enjoy point-to-point transportation to their workplace/school/destination; That real time motorcycle route mapping is adequate and serviceable to the riding population as it meets the standards of functionality, reliability, usability, maintainability, and portability; That the real time motorcycle route mapping works effectively with the embedded system that caters to the faced-faced lifestyles of the riding population without sacrificing the standards of the system used; and That the real time motorcycle taxi route mapping may be adopted for a fast, easy, accessible, and reliable transport system in NCR.

Consequently, the study recommended to develop and provide more information about the different roads interlocking to the route mapping developed for a better transport mobility of the riders and passengers; enhance the system flexibility based on uses and functions by providing more interaction capabilities for a smooth transition of transportation; Improve the systems Graphical User Interface (GUI) for a better appreciation and usability of the route mapping; enhance system performance and operation by providing a stable internet connectivity; Maintain system portability by checking and regular computer specification performance and back-ups; and Future researches may be encouraged with the latest software characteristics to be tested for a better digitized alternative route mapping for other regions.

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